

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D3.1. Guideline of a comprehensive validation and certification procedure to ensure safe CAD systems

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ADS	Automated driving systems
ASAM	Association for standardisation of automation and measuring systems
CAD	Connected and automated driving
CAV	Connected and automated vehicle
CC	Common criteria
DGPS	Differential global positioning system
DTT	Dynamic driving task
EAL	Evaluation assurance level
FMI	Functional mockup interface
FMU	Functional mockup unit
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system
KET	Key enabling technologies
ODD	Operational design domain
OEDR	Object and event detection and response
OSI	Open simulation interface
MRM	Minimal risk manoeuvre
PP	Protection profiles
RSU	Roadside units
SAR	Security assurance requirements
SFR	Security functional requirements
ST	Security target
TARA	Threat analysis and risk assessment
TOE	Target of evaluation
UML	Unified modeling language
VRU	Vulnerable road users
V2I	Vehicle to infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to vehicle
XiL	X in the loop

Executive Summary

This report documents the HEADSTART process, which validates driving functions regarding its safety performance. It was designed based on the HEADSTART methodology. The main parts of this methodology are found in the developed process. The process is divided into further sub-steps, which each addresses a different task that needs to be executed to go through to process and to get to the result if the driving function fulfils all the defined requirements. In subsequent tasks in HEADSTART, the methodology and procedure will be used and validated to see if steps are missing, do not work in the way they were intended or need to be refined.

The deliverable transforms the process into a procedure by describing each task/process step. The difference between the two terms is that a process describes what to do, and a procedure describes how to do it. This provides instructions on how the process and its tasks should be executed. The procedure is divided into different phases, each of which has a main responsible person. This can be a company or organisation, but also a concrete person. As soon as this person changes, a new phase begins. These phases are: Scenario Selection, Scenario Allocation, Testing Method Coordination, Field Testing, Virtual Testing, XiL Testing, Proving Ground Testing, Cyber Security and Evaluation.

A main focus of the HEADSTART project are CAD Key Enabling Technologies (V2X communication, positioning and cyber security). Since it was not possible to use the same process steps for all three KETs, they had to be dealt with differently. Communication and positioning could be integrated into the main process most of the time. Only in the Scenario Allocation phase did these technologies have to be treated separately. This was solved with a separate branch in the process, which, however, is very strongly linked to the main process. Cyber Security, on the other hand, has different requirements and was therefore dealt with in a separate phase.

This report describes each phase using the same template to show entry and exit criteria, necessary inputs, needed resources, roles and tasks within the phase. Then each of the tasks is described in more detail. In some cases, open points remain at this time of the project. Things like exact data formats, interfaces or details in the workflow of some tasks will be worked out later in the work package/project. Perhaps, in the course of the project and during the validation of the procedure, gaps will be discovered that were overlooked in theory. These have to be corrected later on.

The procedure, like the methodology, is something that can and will change and refine in the course of the project. This deliverable presents the current procedure and describes it in the highest possible level of detail on which further work in the project can be based.

1 Introduction

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a European project funded under Horizon 2020 Framework Programme within the call ART-01-2018 (the type: Research and Innovation action).

The five objectives of the HEADSTART project comprise:

- OBJECTIVE 1: IDENTIFY - Create a dynamic catalogue of existing methods, procedures and tools for testing, validation and certification considering multi-stakeholder requirements.
- OBJECTIVE 2: HARMONISE - Harmonisation of existing testing and validation approaches taking into account other industries and domains.
- OBJECTIVE 3: DEFINE & DEVELOP - Define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives.
- OBJECTIVE 4: DEMONSTRATE - Demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through the testing of relevant CAD use cases.
- OBJECTIVE 5: REACH CONSENSUS - Reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network of CAD testing to promote adoption of the project results considering multi-stakeholder needs.

The procedure described in this deliverable addresses Objective 3. It is based on the methodology, which is shown in section 1.1. Then the approach which the methodology was transformed into a procedure is described in section 1.2. Last, an overview of the high-level process is shown in section 1.3.

A crucial external source for the process is the so-called target group. In the HEADSTART project, there are three different target groups:

- Testing and validation (development): e.g. OEMs,
- Assessment - Consumer testing: e.g. Euro NCAP
- Certification (type approval): e.g. Type approval authorities & Technical services

1.1 Methodology

The methodology of the HEADSTART project was developed in work package 2 and published in deliverable 2.1 in detail. It is centred around a scenario-based testing approach for the safety validation of connected and automated vehicles. The processes and procedures presented in this deliverable are directly derived from the methodology.

The proposed methodology does not consider the identification and characterization of relevant scenarios as it instead focuses on the use of such scenarios as input to the assessment framework by assuming that such scenarios are available from specific databases. Nonetheless, a possible workflow regarding database mechanics can be seen at the top of Figure 1, where field, aerial, and accident data, as well as simulator studies, are considered. Additionally, expert knowledge is used to insert additional scenarios that may not (yet) be covered by the respective scenario database to ensure completeness as much as possible.

In the first step of the methodology, the driving function and its functionalities need to be defined. This includes the definition of the respective operational design domain (ODD), which defines the operating domain of the function in terms of, e.g., road network, traffic participants, and weather [1]. The minimum risk manoeuvre (MRM) as well as the actual real-time operational and tactical functions required to operate the vehicle in on-road traffic, needs to be defined as well for evaluation purposes [2] [1]. Additionally, specific requirements derived from the key enabling technologies (KETs) defined in the HEADSTART project (communication, positioning, and cyber security) need to be considered as well during the definition of the associated use case.

Based on this extensive definition of the driving function implemented in the vehicle under test (VUT), which needs to be safety evaluated, a query for the respective scenario database needs to be defined. How queries are

formulated is specific for the scenario database. Keyword-based queries are a possible option. That query returns suitable scenarios in the form of logical scenario definitions and parameter distributions in a specific output format. In the methodology block *Selection of relevant scenarios and stochastic variations* (see Figure 1), the scenarios from the database are checked against the functional requirements from the driving function to ensure completeness. The output of this block is a set of concrete scenarios that were parameterized based on the distributions from the database, additionally ensuring that all chosen parameter combinations lead to test cases within the defined boundaries of the driving function.

In the subsequent block (*Allocation of scenarios*) the concrete scenarios, enriched with relevant parameters from the defined KETs, are allocated to three different test methods based on their respective capabilities. Thus, the allocation determines the optimal mapping of concrete scenarios on different test capabilities. Those three test methods (*proving ground, virtual testing, Xil-based testing*) should complement each other in the safety validation of the driving function. While proving ground tests are expensive and cannot cover the wide variety of tests, they offer the most reliable results in terms of realism. On the other hand, virtual tests principally should be able to cover all realistic variations in tests, but virtual models are only approximate representations of the actual real-world systems. A combination of virtual and real tests is executed as XiL tests, whereby certain elements are real, while others are simulated using virtual models. The actual allocation between those test methods depends on the requirements from the defined concrete scenarios on the specific test environment.

Since it is not possible for field testing to derive actual test cases including all layers from the concrete scenarios, the focus in HEADSTART is to evaluate relevant parameters from the KETs (specifically communication and positioning). After the test execution, the evaluation takes place. All generated test data from all the test methods are compared and based on pre-defined key performance indicators (KPIs) and pass/fail – criteria, the success of the safety validation is determined. Results from the evaluation can be redirected to the selection of relevant scenarios to test certain edge cases in a more detailed way. Finally, the result is given as output to the user [3].

FIGURE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE OVERALL METHODOLOGY

1.2 Approach

The input for the work was the methodology described in detail in Deliverable 2.1 and briefly shown in the previous section. As a deliverable of this task, we developed a procedure for testing, validation and certification of CAD functionalities within the project.

To achieve this goal, the approach of Figure 2 was used. The methodology was transformed into a high-level process that includes the same process steps as the methodology itself. Starting from this high-level process, the individual process steps were elaborated in more detail, and even new process steps have been added where necessary. Draft versions of the process and process steps were regularly discussed with the project partners, and feedback was integrated into the next version. This resulted in an increasingly detailed process, which was presented in the form of a UML-based activity diagram. In the end, the process became so detailed that it could not be represented in one figure in this deliverable. Therefore, the chapters (which are divided according to the phases of the procedure) only show a reference to the respective section of the process. The high-level process is shown as a whole in Figure 3. To simplify the representation, it does not follow the conventions of the activity diagram.

Once the process was agreed upon by the project partners, the next step was to transform it into a procedure. The difference between process and procedure is briefly summarized as:

- *A process is about what to do*
- *A procedure is how to do it*

FIGURE 2: TRANSFORMATION OF THE METHODOLOGY TO A PROCEDURE

To transform the process into a procedure, an already existing template was used [4]. According to this template, the procedure is divided into different phases, each of which has a main responsible person that oversees, organises and manages the phase. This can be a company, organisation or a concrete person. The phases of the HEADSTART procedure are executed mostly sequentially in time, but in case of the testing methods can also run in parallel. The phases are:

- Scenario Selection (chapter 2)
- Scenario Allocation (chapter 3)
- Testing Method Coordination (chapter 4)
- Field Testing (chapter 5)
- Virtual Testing (chapter 6)
- XiL Testing (chapter 7)

- Proving Ground Testing (chapter 8)
- Cyber Security (chapter 0)
- Evaluation (chapter 0)

1.3 High-level Process

The high-level representation of the process was the first step from the methodology to a detailed process. It is clearly visible that the basic structure for the process has been adopted from the methodology. Furthermore, the representation is suitable to get a first overview of the process before the following chapters describe the individual subtasks in detail. All phases listed in chapter 1.2 can be found in the high-level process (see Figure 3).

FIGURE 3: HIGH-LEVEL PROCESS

The high-level process is not described here since the following chapters provide an in-depth description of the procedure for the different process steps. In some of the process steps, the term scenario is mentioned. When the document talks about scenarios, it is always about concrete scenarios. If logical scenarios are meant, this is mentioned explicitly.

1.4 Key Enabling Technologies in the Process

Safe Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) will require certain functionality at vehicle level, but also at system level. The system will consist of vehicles, may also include other users, and possibly also build system of systems. Solving this will require certain Key Enabling Technologies. Three KETs were listed during the application phase:

- V2X communication
- Positioning
- Cyber Security

These technologies are very important for the project and are therefore included in the process. However, during development it quickly became clear that cyber security cannot be described with the same process steps as communication and positioning. For this reason, the tasks for Cyber Security were moved to a separate branch of the process, which is connected to the rest of the process (see chapter 9.3).

Communication and positioning has been integrated into the main process and all necessary tasks can be performed in the general task. The only exception is in the Scenario Allocation phase (see chapter 3). There is a separate branch for the two remaining KETs to ensure the correct allocation of scenarios that have been enriched by communication or positioning requirements. When it comes to testing, special equipment or infrastructure is needed, but this will be prepared and taken care of in the same process steps as it would for test cases that contain no communication or positioning requirements.

In order to avoid misunderstandings, these two technologies are not mentioned as KETs in the process, but are addressed explicitly, since cyber security is dealt with in a dedicated section.

2 Scenario Selection

The procedure starts with the "Scenario Selection" phase. The necessary input for this phase is a detailed description of the capabilities of a driving function, which should be validated with this procedure. The content of this description includes the dynamic driving task (DDT) as defined in [3]. With the DDT, all the real-time operational and tactical functions needed to operate the vehicle equipped with the driving function are defined. Relevant operational functions are lateral and longitudinal motion control, as well as monitoring the driving environment. Tactical functions include, e.g. manoeuvre planning. The monitoring of the driving environment is together with the object and event response execution (a tactical and operational function) collectively referred to as object and event detection and response (OEDR).

Another necessary input is the operational design domain (ODD) of the vehicle in which the function-under-test is integrated. The ODD defines under which circumstances the automated vehicle can execute the DDT and at the same time defines the limit of operation for the described function. A potential description of the ODD can include, amongst other aspects, the maximum speed of the ego vehicle, geographic location ("geofencing") as well as a specific environment description.

In this first phase of the procedure, logical scenarios are extracted from a database, based on a query, and, if necessary, additional logical scenarios are added manually. Next, the logical scenarios are evaluated and ranked according to their relevance. After that, the trustworthy and relevant scenarios, including their parameter distribution, are assigned to one or more test methods in the next phase. Table 1 gives a short description of the phase.

TABLE 1: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "SCENARIO SELECTION"

Phase: Scenario Selection

Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner

Description: Scenarios are queried from a database and ranked in order of relevance for the safety evaluation of a driving function.

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Dynamic driving tasks
- ODD (Operational Design Domain)
- Use case
- Data from a database in the form of scenario descriptions
- Set of KPIs
- Additional scenarios and expert knowledge (optional)
- Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (for cyber security tests)

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Trustworthy and relevant scenario descriptions with parameter distributions

Roles:

- Driving function owner
- Database owner
- Scenario experts

Resources or Assets:

- Database of logical scenarios

Task:

- Define a query
- Extract scenarios from the database
- Check if scenarios are inside ODD
- Check if ODD is sufficiently covered
- Check if all functionalities are tested
- Include additional scenarios with parameter distribution (optional)
- Add feedback from the evaluation
- Assess the relevance of parameters
- Check availability of parameter distribution
- Assess relevance based on expert knowledge (optional)
- Assess the relevance of parameter distribution
- Check if the parameter combination is feasible

The individual tasks (process steps) are described below:

Define a query (see Figure 4):

In this first process step, a query must be created using the information from the dynamic driving task (DDT), the operational design domain (ODD) and the use case. With this type of information, the functional capabilities of the driving function, as well as the boundaries, are defined. Since there is no standardized format for describing the ODD yet, formalizing a particular query for a database depends on the actual database. Using a keyword-based query is one of the possibilities in order to ensure that the requested scenarios from the database are inside the specified ODD.

Extract scenarios from the database (see Figure 4):

In this task, the generated query is passed to the scenario database. The database selects the relevant data and converts it to the requested output format. Currently, OpenSCENARIO 1.0¹ is the most promising data format specification for describing the actions of traffic participants in a specific environment, and it is therefore expected that scenario databases will use this or some future development branch of this specification. For specifying the respective environment in which a concrete scenario should happen, additionally, OpenDRIVE descriptions can be provided. The selected concrete scenarios are then made available in a data bundle for further usage in the procedure, ideally including parameter distributions.

FIGURE 4: PART 1 OF THE PHASE “SCENARIO SELECTION” FROM THE DETAILED PROCESS

Check if scenarios are inside ODD (see Figure 5):

In this step, it is checked whether the scenarios are within the ODD and thus suitable for further processing. As a standardized description of ODDs is still pending (not in terms of taxonomy but as a format for usage in test cases

¹ <https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openscenario/>

and coverage analyses) checking if a scenario happens in- or outside the defined ODD depends on the actual complexity of the ODD itself. If a scenario is identified to be outside the ODD, the scenario itself and the corresponding files are removed from the list of scenarios.

FIGURE 5: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO SELECTION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Check if ODD is sufficiently covered (see Figure 5):

After checking in the previous step whether specific scenarios need to be removed, this task is about checking whether the scenarios from the database already cover a significantly large part of the ODD in order to ensure an adequate safety evaluation of the driving function. In order to quantify the ODD coverage with the selected scenarios from the database, as mentioned before, the ODD itself needs to be described in a quantifiable, standardized manner to enable a comparison with the available scenario descriptions, including the parameter

distributions. Another option would be to use expert knowledge to evaluate if enough of the ODD is covered. If this is the case, it can be continued with the step "Check if all functionalities are tested". If additional scenarios are needed to cover the ODD sufficiently, the process step "Include additional scenarios with parameter distribution" must be executed.

Check if all functionalities are tested (see Figure 5):

Like the previous step, this task checks whether the existing scenarios are sufficient to test all relevant functionalities of the driving function. One way to identify this is to use the provided input from the driving function, respectively the DDT and especially the OEDR, which is part of the DDT. With the OEDR, mapping specific events (e.g. braking of vehicle in front) to responses of the automated vehicle, such an evaluation can be carried out. This can be done by checking (for every event/response pair defined) if the execution of the concrete scenarios triggers all the essential events. If for example, an event/response pair is "obstacle on-road/evade", but none of the scenarios includes an obstacle on the road, then this type of scenarios needs to be added to the existing ones.

If every basic functionality (which is equal to every event/response pair defined in the OEDR) is tested, it can be continued with the step "Add feedback from evaluation". Otherwise, additional scenarios must be added, which has to be done in the step "Include additional scenarios with parameter distribution". These additional scenarios must cover the identified gaps in terms of testing the defined capabilities and functionalities of the driving function.

Include additional scenarios with parameter distribution (optional) (see Figure 5):

This process step is only executed if the ODD is not sufficiently covered by the existing scenarios from the database or not all functionalities of the driving function are tested. If the coverage is sufficient with the existing selected scenarios, this task will not be executed. Since the goal of this process step is to add missing scenarios that have to fulfil specific requirements, it is crucial to have one or more experts who can plan and create such scenarios in the same data format as the already existing ones. Then it returns to the main branch of the process, where it is checked once again if there are enough scenarios to test all relevant parts.

Add feedback from the evaluation (see Figure 6):

Although the previous steps have ensured that the scenarios cover all important parts of the driving function, it must also be possible to include previously used test cases. One reason for this may be that the driving function has already passed through the process once, and specific tests have not resulted in the fulfilment of one or more key performance indicators (KPIs). These test cases are rechecked for their data format to ensure compatibility.

Assess the relevance of parameters (see Figure 6):

Scenario databases aim for combining similar scenario descriptions (on an abstract level) and separately store the probability distribution for the occurrence of a particular parameter value inside such a scenario description. In order to reach enough coverage to form a safety case for the driving function, it is therefore essential to evaluate one scenario description with as many different parameter combinations as required for a complete assessment. If many parameters are to be tested in their full range, the effort of the tests increases, so it is necessary to evaluate the importance of the individual parameters. Analysing each of the different logical scenario descriptions extracted from the specific database leads to parameters that of higher relevance than others. What is especially important there is to evaluate what information the ego vehicles driving function extracts from the scenario environment in order to assess this parameter relevance (e.g. velocity of the cut-in vehicle seems more important for a decisive scenario execution than the width of the road shoulder). Additionally, parameters which do not influence the scenario execution since they would lead to the concrete scenario being outside of the defined ODD have to be erased from the scenario descriptions. Examples for this could be road elevation or a lateral profile on

Assess relevance based on expert knowledge (optional) (see Figure 6):

If the parameter distribution for a specific scenario description or for certain parameters of this scenario is not available, the distribution along the parameter range must be defined manually. Expert knowledge could be one way of gaining missing information since the expert may have specific information based on the use case and scenario description. In general, the applicable parameter range is important, most important. Additionally, a possible approach could be to assign a uniform distribution as a probability of occurrence for a specific parameter. For some parameters, a gaussian distribution with the maximum in the middle of the specified parameter range could be a suitable approach.

Assess the relevance of parameter distribution (see Figure 7):

In this step of the first phase of the procedure, it needs to be defined, which end of the parameter range potentially leads to the more relevant parameter combinations. This step is necessary since the most common parameter values (extracted either from the database or defined by expert knowledge) usually do not lead to the most challenging or safety-critical parameter combinations. In order to receive a relevance ranking for the concrete scenario descriptions, one approach could be to combine the occurrence probability of the parameter value with its actual relevance. For specific parameters, this process is more straightforward than for others. The speed of a cut-in vehicle after the actual cut-in is more relevant for the safety evaluation if it is lower because this leads a higher braking demand of the ego vehicle and therefore to more potentially dangerous situations. How this relevance evolves along the range of the parameter is usually unknown. A straightforward approach for a first assessment could be to assign a linear parameter (between 1 and 0) for the relevance. The end of the parameter range, which is seen as more relevant, is assigned 1 as parameter relevance and vice versa.

This process is not feasible for every parameter since the distinction between “relevant” and “not relevant” is not clear without further analysing the parameters and their impact on the scenario. Assessing the impact relevance of individual parameters as well as parameter combinations for specific scenario descriptions is still an open question and therefore, an active research topic.

Check if the parameter combination is feasible (see Figure 7):

When the parameter and their respective ranges are combined to concrete scenarios, a few feasibility checks need to be executed in order to ensure that the gathered parameter combination is realistically possible.

Those feasibility checks should at least answer the following questions:

- Is the parameter combination physically possible?
 - For the example of a cut-in scenario, the cut-in vehicle must first surpass the ego vehicle in order to cut-in (assuming the vehicle to cut-in always start behind or at most at the same height of the ego vehicle). Therefore, the velocity of the cut-in vehicle must be higher than the velocity of the ego vehicle in order to ensure that. This could be done with a simple check of the velocity start values of the vehicles or more sophisticated to analyse the longitudinal motion of the scenario participants before the potential cut-in.
- Is the parameter combination interesting?
 - If, for a junction-based scenario, the trajectories of the traffic participants (including the ego vehicle) never collide, the scenario could be categorized as not interesting. Another example would be a cut-in scenario where the vehicle (which should cut-in in front of the ego vehicle and starts behind the ego) always has a lower velocity than the ego vehicle.
- Are traffic laws obeyed?

- If the result of some parameter combinations is the violation of traffic regulation, the scenario may be removed, or some threshold values are defined which enable some traffic law violation (which is in some cases more realistic).

After those feasibility checks, the number of parameter combinations should have been reduced to only the concrete scenario descriptions which are physically possible, interesting and are permitted by traffic regulations.

FIGURE 7: PART 4 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO SELECTION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

3 Scenario Allocation

The second phase of the proposed procedure for safety validation of driving functions is the allocation of the selected scenarios to the different testing methods. Various inputs are needed for the execution of this phase. Firstly, the trustworthy and relevant scenarios of the previous scenario selection phase. Secondly, the testing capabilities of each test method needs to be gathered in a structured way and made available to the scenario allocation phase of the procedure. Additionally, the defined key performance indicators (KPIs) are also required as input for this specific phase of the procedure. This defined set of criteria also serves as an input for the evaluation. Lastly, the different target groups influence the decision-making process for the scenario allocation as well. The target groups in HEADSTART are:

- Testing and validation (development): e.g. OEMs,
- Assessment - Consumer testing: e.g. Euro NCAP
- Certification (type approval): e.g. Type approval authorities & Technical services

TABLE 2: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "SCENARIO ALLOCATION"

Phase: Scenario Allocation

Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner

Description: Scenarios are allocated to the testing methods. Additional functional requirements that are not covered by scenarios from the database will either be integrated or allocated separately.

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Trustworthy and relevant scenario descriptions with parameter distributions
- Dynamic driving task
- Use case
- Target group
- Set of capabilities of the different testing methods
- Database (optional)
- Set of criteria
- List of additional requirements (optional)

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Scenarios allocated to each of the testing methods

Roles:

- Driving function owner
- Target group
- Test Engineers
- Scenario experts (optional)

Resources or Assets:

- Database
- Test method capabilities
- Additional requirements (optional)

Phase: Scenario Allocation

Task:

- Define capabilities for virtual testing
- Define capabilities for XiL testing
- Define capabilities for proving ground testing
- Compile to a map of capability
- Extract logical scenario elements
- Match XiL capabilities with a scenario
- Align parameter ranges of scenario and XiL
- Match proving ground capabilities with a scenario
- Align parameter ranges of scenario and proving ground
- Match virtual testing capabilities with a scenario
- Assign a concrete scenario to a testing method(s)
- Identify additional requirements that are not covered by scenarios from the scenario database
- Get requirement (optional)
- Assign the requirement to a testing method (optional)
- Integrate requirement into a scenario data format (optional)
- Get test case for requirement (optional)
- Extract information for positioning/communication (optional)
- Get logical layer for communication with parameter distribution (optional)
- Get logical layer for positioning with parameter distribution (optional)
- Select parameter (optional)

Define capabilities for virtual testing (see Figure 9):

Virtual testing, just like XiL testing and proving ground testing has its capabilities and restrictions. Therefore, it is necessary to define those capabilities to ensure the correct allocation of the scenarios. The division into the three categories “Sensor”, “Environment” and “Vehicle Dynamics” were first introduced in deliverable 2.1 of the HEADSTART project and represent the common elements needed of a validation framework for driving functions. Simulation models or the real world can represent these three categories. An example of this representation can be seen in Figure 8.

FIGURE 8: MAP OF CAPABILITIES FOR THE DIFFERENT TEST METHODS (EXAMPLE, BLUE: PROVING GROUND, ORANGE: XiL-BASED TESTING, YELLOW: VIRTUAL TESTING)

The fidelity of the simulation models can be divided into three levels, which are explained in Table 3.

TABLE 3: EXPLANATION OF THE TERMS “LOW”, “MEDIUM” AND “HIGH” FIDELITY SIMULATION MODELS

Model Fidelity:	Low	Medium	High
Sensor Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Object list-based Based on ground truth data from simulation environment in the FOV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on ideal models Adding statistical failure rates Modified object list entries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on physical principles of respective sensor type
Environment Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The environment must be able to place different objects the simulation and update their location and orientation accordingly. 2D-representation could be sufficient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3D-representation of objects No physics-rendering engine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High fidelity sensor models force the most requirements on environment models. Usually a simulation engine based on ray-tracing is needed. Potentially also real materials and textures
Vehicle Dynamics Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Point mass model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single track vehicle model Double track vehicle model ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full 6 DOF vehicle model

According to this definition, the responsible person for virtual testing has to report the level of fidelity for his simulation models to determine the capability of this testing method.

Define capabilities for XiL testing (see Figure 9):

The definition of the capabilities for XiL testing is done similarly as for virtual testing. The difference here is that not only simulation models are used. Depending on what is in the loop, real components also have to be considered, and the capabilities of the hardware/infrastructure that is used to perform the tests need to be defined as well. For the definition of the real-world capabilities, the possibility to measure specific effects (e.g. movement of actors) during scenario execution needs to be considered as well.

Define capabilities for proving ground testing (see Figure 9):

The procedure is the same as for the other testing methods with the difference that only real components are used. The capabilities of the components have to be recorded precisely to ensure that scenarios that are assigned to proving ground testing can be performed on this proving ground. A proposed structure to follow is the layer-based approach describing the different elements of scenarios based on categories, as introduced by [1]. Additionally, the possibility to measure certain effects during scenario execution needs to be defined as well, as this directly influences the scenario allocation, as specific KPIs may need specific parameters to be measured.

Compile map of capabilities (see Figure 9):

This step combines the information that results out of the previous three tasks. The capabilities of the three testing methods are combined in a file and are passed on as input to further tasks in the "Scenario Allocation" phase. Additionally to the defined capabilities based on the common categories of validation frameworks, capabilities in terms of key enabling technologies like positioning and communication should be defined as well to assess in later stages of the procedure if an allocation of scenarios with these types of parameters is possible. For the third KET in the HEADSTART project, cyber security, a separate phase was defined and is described in section 9.

FIGURE 9: PART 1 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Extract logical scenario elements (see Figure 12):

To be able to compare the real-world capabilities of the different test methods (XiL and proving ground) with the actual scenarios to be tested, the different elements in the scenario are categorized into the different layers proposed by [5]. These layers and their respective content can be seen in Figure 10. Each parameter of a scenario can be classified into these layers, serving as an important way to structure the comparison with the actual test method.

Match XiL capabilities with scenario (see Figure 12):

To assess if concrete scenarios can be executed utilizing XiL-based testing, the provided capabilities for this testing method are compared with the actual requirements defined by the concrete scenarios that need to be executed. Based on that, the first step is to make sure that the real components of the specific XiL-based testing approach can represent the elements defined by the scenario description. This comparison can be made for all the scenarios belonging to the same category (defined by the logical scenario) at once. If such a representation is not possible, the testing method is not feasible for all the associated concrete scenarios.

Since XiL-based testing methods often represent precise setups regarding vehicle motion (e.g. brake testbeds), the potential trajectory of the ego vehicle needs to be compared to the possible representation by the XiL-based test method. The potential trajectory can be derived from the provided OEDR table by checking the expected response to a particular event (e.g. vehicle cut-in). This event needs to be derived from the scenario. If this

evaluation leads to the conclusion that a realistic execution of this type of scenario is not possible, this specific test method is not appropriate for these scenarios (for all of the scenarios belonging to one logical scenario).

FIGURE 10: FIVE-LAYER MODEL FOR A SYSTEMATIC DESCRIPTION OF TRAFFIC SCENARIOS (POTENTIAL DIGITAL LAYER 6 NOT DISPLAYED). GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION FROM [6] AND INSPIRED BY [5]

Align parameter ranges of scenario and XiL (see Figure 12):

In this step of the scenario allocation phase, each of the parameters belonging to the respective scenario description is aligned with the capabilities of the XiL-based testing method. Usually, this only makes sense for the parameters that actively influence the criticality of the scenario or at least parameters that influence the testing method and the driving function. This should, at least partly, already have been done in the previous phase of the procedure, the scenario selection phase. An effective and automated way to identify those critical parameters is an active topic of research.

The possible parameter ranges (if a particular restriction is necessary) are essential pieces of information for the final allocation of the scenario to the different test methods. A qualitative example of such parameter range restrictions can be seen in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11: QUALITATIVE EXAMPLE OF PARAMETER RANGE RESTRICTIONS

FIGURE 12: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Match proving ground capabilities with scenario (see Figure 13):

To assess if concrete scenarios can be executed on the proving ground, the provided capabilities for this testing method are compared with the actual requirements defined by the concrete scenarios that need to be executed. Based on that, the first step is to make sure that the proving ground can represent the elements defined by the scenario description. This comparison can be made for all the scenarios belonging to the same category (defined by the logical scenario) at once. If such a representation is not possible, the testing method is not feasible for all the associated concrete scenarios. This could be for example the case if the evaluation of layer 1 (road layout) has the result that the available space at the proving ground is not enough to execute the scenario (this could be the case for the whole logical scenario or for a specific concrete scenario that belong to the logical scenario). Restrictions usually stem from speed limits, available space, available road layout, or limitations to the impact speed of physical targets.

Align parameter ranges of scenario and proving ground (see Figure 13):

In this step of the scenario allocation phase, each of the parameters belonging to the respective scenario description is aligned with the capabilities of the proving ground. Usually, this only makes sense for the parameters that actively influence the criticality of the scenario or at least parameters that influence the testing method and the driving function.

The possible parameter ranges (if a particular restriction is necessary) are important information for the final allocation of the scenario to the different test methods

Match virtual testing capabilities with scenario (see Figure 13):

For each specific use case, the respective driving function imposes certain minimum requirements to the virtual testing capabilities. For a truck platooning use case, this could, for example, be a highly detailed longitudinal vehicle dynamics model to correctly assess potential implications of specific actions of particular trucks in the platoon. The level of fidelity, therefore, highly depends on the actual use case.

This step of the scenario allocation phase should, therefore, ensure that the available virtual testing capabilities meet all those minimum requirements emerging from the specific use case. If this is not the case, the virtual testing capabilities need to be extended in the specific categories, as without the usage of virtual testing forming a statistical safety argument is not possible.

FIGURE 13: PART 3 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Assign a concrete scenario to a testing method(s) (see Figure 16):

In this step of the scenario allocation phase, the actual allocation of concrete scenarios to the available test methods takes place.

Before presenting a possible approach for allocating scenarios to test methods, all the available information, as well as the underlying paradigms, are listed:

- At the beginning of this procedure step, the possible test method(s) for every specific concrete scenario is available.
- While allocating actual concrete scenarios, which can then be transformed to test cases, keeping the concrete scenarios organized and grouped based on their associated logical scenario, is a key component of the proposed approach.
- The actual allocation of concrete scenarios to test methods is a process highly influenced by the executing target group.

In Figure 14, a qualitative example of the situation for a specific logical scenario at the beginning of the allocation process can be seen. Every concrete scenario was assigned to the possible test methods (based on the stated capabilities), explicitly allowing the assignment of one concrete scenario to multiple test methods. To additionally validate the virtual components of the test methods XiL and virtual testing, at least one baseline scenario should be selected. This baseline scenario needs to be executed on every test method.

The next step is to assign each concrete scenario to a testing method. Beginning with XiL (since it is the most specific test method, e.g. a brake testbed restricts the possible ego-motion), each concrete scenario which is possible with this test method, is assigned to it, ranked after the criticality of the scenario. Criticality can be understood as a critical situation for the vehicle under test (equipped with the driving function) as well as a potentially dangerous test case (high risk during test execution, e.g., risk of truck tip over during lane change manoeuvre).

Since XiL and proving ground are not scalable test methods (unlike virtual testing) this is done until a set boundary for the number of concrete scenarios is met. The remaining concrete scenarios have to be assigned to the virtual testing (if possible, based on the capabilities. Otherwise, additional capabilities are requested).

FIGURE 14: QUALITATIVE EXAMPLE OF CONCRETE SCENARIOS BEING TESTABLE BY DIFFERENT TEST METHODS

Additionally, the occurrence probability of concrete scenarios, for a specific logical scenario, can be a deciding factor for the scenario allocation. Usually, typical traffic scenarios (low complexity and high probability of occurrence) are tested on the proving ground. In contrast, critical scenarios and edge cases are, due to their complexity, much more suitable for XiL and virtual testing. This can be seen in a qualitative example in Figure 15. The test method proving ground (shaded in blue) is used for the typical traffic scenarios, with some slight overlap to more critical scenarios. The test method XiL (shaded in orange) is usually used for more critical traffic scenarios (since some parts of the environment are shifted to virtual elements) as well as some edge cases. The test method virtual testing (shaded in yellow) on the other hand, is usually leveraged for edge cases.

FIGURE 15: OCCURRENCE PROBABILITY OF CONCRETE SCENARIOS FOR A SPECIFIC LOGICAL SCENARIO

FIGURE 16: PART 4 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Identify additional requirements that are not covered by scenarios from the database (see Figure 17):

If one is only interested in parameters that can be covered by the scenario database, then the next four process steps that are marked "optional" are not required. The allocation of the scenarios to the testing methods is then only done in the left branch of the scenario allocation phase (described in the tasks above). However, there are also several parameters/requirements that (at least currently) are not available in the database (regarding the Headstart KETs positioning and communication). For these parameters, a separate way to allocate them to a testing method is needed. For this purpose, there is this right branch of this phase. The process is designed such that it is not limited to the HEADSTART project, and therefore it is essential to cover all kind of requirements, which can be done with this optional branch.

Get requirement (optional) (see Figure 17):

Entering this part of the process means that there is at least one additional parameter that is not covered by the scenarios from the database. If there is only one requirement/parameter, this one is selected. If there are several

requirements, the first one is taken, and the next process steps are executed for this requirement. The procedure is then repeated for the next requirement.

FIGURE 17: PART 5 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Assign the requirement to a testing method (optional) (see Figure 18):

This process step is executed if the requirement is not already assigned to a specific testing method or methods. This check has been implemented because individual requirements may require one or more specific testing methods or because some testing methods are preferred from the start.

In this task, the requirements that are not yet allocated to a testing method will be allocated. This has to be done manually by experts. In this step, it is possible to allocate the requirement to one or more testing methods. In this case allocation to field testing is also possible. While the scenarios from the database are all available in the same data format, it is not specified how these requirements are formatted. This can range from a standardized code to pseudo code to a textual description.

FIGURE 18: PART 6 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Integrate requirement into a scenario data format (optional) (see Figure 19):

Since this branch of the scenario allocation phase was kept as general as possible in order to be able to deal with all requirements, it is difficult to estimate in which form these requirements will be formulated. Therefore, it has to be distinguished first whether the parameters can be represented by the data format in which the scenarios are available from the database or not. If this is not the case, the requirement must be embedded in a customized test case (see "Get test case for requirement (optional)").

If it is possible, however, it has to be decided in which scenarios the requirement should be integrated. Since the preferred testing method(s) is/are already known, only the scenarios from the main branch of scenario allocation that have already been assigned to these testing methods are selected. Now the scenarios in which the additional requirements should be integrated have to be selected. At the end of this task, there will be a certain number of scenarios that have been enriched with that requirement. Finally, it has to be verified that the change of the code does not lead to a violation of the standards of this data format.

Get test case for requirement (optional) (see Figure 19):

This process step is performed if one or more testing methods have already been assigned to the requirement, and it is not possible to integrate the requirement into the scenario data format used by the database. As in the step "Assign the requirement to a testing method", the assignment of a test case in this step has to be done manually by experts. If there is no further requirement, the scenario allocation phase can be exited. Otherwise, the process continues with the next requirement.

FIGURE 19: PART 7 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Extract information for positioning/communication (optional) (see Figure 20):

In parallel to matching capabilities of the different testing methods with the defined scenario descriptions and parameter distributions, additional scenario layers (e.g. as Key Enabling Technologies) need to be considered in the procedure. This branch can be ignored if the driving function under test, and therefore, the functional requirements are fully covered with the gathered scenarios.

In particular, two main KETs are considered as an example: positioning and communication.

In this step, the situation, as defined by the selected scenario is analysed, in order to identify the impact of the KETs (positioning/communication), as described in the functional requirements, on the ego-vehicle and the scene in general. This impact analysis needs to be guided to distinguish the conditional aspects that each KET introduces into the scene.

FIGURE 20: PART 8 OF THE PHASE "SCENARIO ALLOCATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Get logical layer for communication with parameter distribution (optional) / Get logical layer for positioning with parameter distribution (optional) (see Figure 20):

As a result of the analysis carried out in the previous step, it is then possible to separate the concepts for each KET (e.g. positioning and communication). The task then shall aim to produce a logical layer for each KET with

additional parameter distributions. This layer needs to be understood as an additional layer that provides descriptive capabilities to the selected scenario. Besides, the defined parameters and distributions can be treated as any other parameter of other layers.

Select parameter (optional) (see Figure 20):

The particularities of each KET shall be addressed at the time of selecting which parameters need to be considered, according to the restrictions the KETs impose over the testing method. For instance, positioning or communication capabilities might not be available or possible in proving ground facilities and therefore need to be identified as “simulation”-only parameter set.

4 Testing Method Coordination

In this phase, the target group decides the order of the allocated scenarios. This step provides the necessary flexibility in the execution of the tests.

TABLE 4: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "TESTING METHOD COORDINATION"

Phase: Testing Method Coordination
Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner
Description: The order of the testing methods is assigned
Entry Criteria/Inputs:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocated scenarios • Target group
Exit Criteria/Outputs:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocated scenarios
Roles:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target group
Resources or Assets:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocated scenarios
Task:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign testing method order

Assign testing method order:

In this task, the allocated scenarios of the previous phase are carried over. Each of these scenarios is assigned to one of the four testing methods. The purpose of this task is to decide which of the testing methods should be executed first. This decision has to be made by the target group to take their priorities into account. It is also

possible to run several testing methods in parallel. Once a decision has been made, the scenarios assigned to this testing method are transferred to the person responsible for this testing method.

After the tests have been completed and evaluated, this phase can be re-entered if further tests are planned. The target group has the decision about the further proceeding again, but now also has the results of the tests already performed to determine the further order of the tests.

5 Field Testing

Field testing needs to be part of a coherent strategy that guarantees the evaluation process complies with and follows the principles of the defined testing methodology. Specifically, for field testing, traceability of results is important. This means that during such tests, the encountered scenarios on the road need to be identified and classified to be able to analyse to which inputs the function-under-test has responded in order to be able to evaluate whether the requirements have been met.

Public roads offer a “real-world laboratory” to support testing and evaluation of Connected and automated vehicle (CAV). Several entities are actively testing prototype Automated Driving Systems (ADS) in public, open-road settings to support ongoing development and refinement.

In addition to allowing a full performance assessment of the prototype systems, public roads expose the systems to a wide variety of real-world conditions related to ODD that would not be feasible with established closed test tracks or simulated approaches

TABLE 5: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "FIELD TESTING"

Phase: Field Testing

Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner

Description: A route will be defined for the allocated scenarios, and the strategy, equipment and infrastructure must be prepared. Then the tests can be conducted, and the test data will be processed to see if the results meet the KPI requirements.

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Allocated scenarios
- Dynamic driving task
- Use case
- KPIs
- KPI requirements

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Test data

Phase: Field Testing

Roles:

- Driving function owner
- Test engineer
- Demonstrator car driver
- Data manager

Resources or Assets:

- Demonstrator car
- Route
- Equipment (sensors, data logger, ...)
- Database

Task:

- Define Route
- Prepare field testing strategy
- Prepare test vehicle equipment
- Prepare infrastructure equipment
- Conduct field tests
- Store test data and add encountered scenarios to the scenario database (2nd part is optional)
- Extract relevant parameters for evaluation
- Compare test data with KPI requirements

Define route (see Figure 21):

Field testing is the only HEADSTART test environment which is not using the scenarios from the database in order to verify the automated driving system because of the lack of controllability. Instead, it is necessary to define a route which includes the identification of suitable routes specific to test the target driving function, via the definition and description of criteria such as the presence or density of elements (e.g., perception blockers, vulnerable road users (VRUs) density).

Firstly, an analysis of the use case shall be done taking under consideration the following inputs: ODD, use case, DDT and the allocated scenarios

Finally, a route or set of routes are defined with the aim of having a reasonable probability of encountering situations which are relevant and the minimization of the total number of test drive kilometres.

FIGURE 21: PART 1 OF THE PHASE "FIELD TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Prepare field testing strategy (see Figure 21):

The validation of an automated vehicle in open roads needs to be planned appropriately because depending on the country where the vehicle will be deployed there will be different regulations that need to be fulfilled in order to conduct the previously defined routes.

In this part of the process, a field testing strategy will be defined, which will contain the following information:

- **Vehicle Under Test setup:** the equipment that needs to be installed in the vehicle for evaluating the automated driving function needs to be described. This will normally be, e.g., data logging systems, reference sensors, context cameras.
- **Driving function dependencies:** In general, the driving function under test may need external activations to be present and considered, including other controlled target vehicles, the existence of HD map services for accurate localization, and/or updated SD maps for navigation.
- **Infrastructure requirements:** Provided the goal to run specific driving functions, technical requirements are put to road infrastructure equipment, e.g., availability of communication base stations, differential global positioning system (DGPS) services. Route-specific equipment or configurations might as well be needed at the instrumented vehicle, such as signal receivers, or V2I credentials.
- **Regulations and exemptions:** Finally, open road testing utterly needs to be defined in the context of the regulatory, insurance and road-operation bodies that facilitate the testing activities under the mandated principles and regulations. In general, instrumented vehicles or functions under test need to acquire the necessary exemptions to allow the use on public roads.

Prepare test vehicle equipment (see Figure 21):

The goal of this activity is to prepare the equipment which is necessary to be installed in the vehicle for field testing.

For this purpose, it is crucial to ensure that the required monitoring signals for the test cases of the vehicle under test are being recorded. Moreover, any equipment which is necessary for the synchronization between the vehicle under test and the infrastructure (for example with controlled test dummies) is taken into account.

The test plan defined in the previous step will contain all the information about which equipment to install in the vehicle and during this activity that equipment will be installed and also a commissioning of the vehicle under test will be done in order to ensure that everything is working properly for conducting the tests in open roads.

Prepare infrastructure equipment (see Figure 22):

Once the vehicle under test is prepared, the next step is to have all the infrastructure equipment prepared according to the requirements defined in the field-testing strategy. These requirements will include, for instance, base stations, DGPS services, and roadside units (RSUs) for connectivity.

The previously defined test plan will contain all the information about which equipment needs to be prepared for this purpose.

Conduct field tests (see Figure 22):

Open road testing needs to be defined to produce results which are evaluable with the same criteria and data format. The goal is to have an effective test case coverage during the field test. As a consequence, such coverage analysis can feedback how much tests are still required, and in which form, defining the required resources (either computational, related to infrastructure, etc.)

Store test data and add encountered scenarios to the scenario database (optional) (see Figure 22):

For this purpose, all the information relevant for the evaluation of the test cases is configured to be recorded in the data logging systems which are inside the vehicle under test.

FIGURE 22: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "FIELD TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Extract relevant parameters for evaluation (see Figure 23):

Each defined route is executed in open roads contains its acceptance criteria where the monitoring signals to be evaluated are defined.

FIGURE 23: PART 3 OF THE PHASE "FIELD TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Compare test data with KPI requirements (see Figure 23):

The last step of the process is to evaluate the routes executed in field testing. This activity uses the previously extracted data from the executed routes and compares it against the KPI requirements. For this purpose, post-processing needs to be done to check if the test has been passed or failed.

6 Virtual Testing

Virtual testing consists of the execution of the allocated scenarios on simulation environments, where all the aspects that describe the scene, sensors, function under test and the vehicle (including its dynamics, see [5]), in the form of parameters, are virtualized and controlled by the simulation framework.

The virtual testing method shall include (as defined in deliverable D2.3) virtual models for the driving function- (under-test), vehicle dynamics, sensors, actuators and virtual environment. In this sense, virtual testing requires the definition of models, as entities which simulate the behaviour or characteristics of each virtual component. For instance, models of sensors represent how a real sensor measures physical magnitudes of the real world, while a model of a scene itself typically includes static elements (e.g. road topologies, buildings, road furniture) and dynamic elements (e.g. models of pedestrians or other vehicles).

As input, virtual testing receives the allocated scenarios, specified according to the testing capabilities of the virtual environment framework, along with the KPIs defined in the procedure to ensure the correct selection of test result variables to be produced.

The virtual testing method is ready for use when all the required components for the specific allocated test cases are identified, available, and validated. The allocated test cases are then injected into the simulation framework, where the tests are conducted using the appropriate hardware and software resources.

TABLE 6: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "VIRTUAL TESTING"

Phase: Virtual Testing

Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner

Description: The strategy for the allocated scenarios, simulation models, and simulation environment must be prepared. Then the tests can be conducted, and the test data will be processed to see if the results meet the KPI requirements.

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Allocated scenarios
- KPIs
- KPI requirements
- Proving ground test data (optional)
- XiL test data (optional)

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Test data

Roles:

- Simulation model/environment owner
- Testing engineer
- Data manager

Phase: Virtual Testing

Resources or Assets:

- Simulation models
- Sensor models
- Simulation environment
- Proving ground test data (optional)
- XiL test data (optional)
- Database

Task:

- Prepare a virtual testing strategy
- Prepare virtual testing
- Validate components (optional)
- Conduct virtual tests
- Store test data
- Extract relevant parameters for evaluation
- Compare test data with KPI requirements

Prepare a virtual testing strategy (see Figure 24):

A strategy is defined to enlist the required steps to set-up the needed resources (SW, HW), interfaces (conversion from domain-specific languages, a mapping between standards, etc.) and metrics to determine the KPI.

The strategy shall include how to validate each model and simulation component. Depending on its nature (sensor, vehicle dynamics or driving function) each component may need to be validated with a different type of rules and tools. For instance, the strategy shall address the need to utilise real data along with simulated data to determine their levels of similarity. In this stage, the vehicle manufacturer shall provide documentation to be audited about what process is used to construct the models, and how they have been validated. The audit should not reveal individual model performances, but if the simulation results for the complete system provide a reliable outcome.

Second, the strategy shall identify the mechanisms to declare allocated test cases as ready for testing, considering aspects such as computational resources available (e.g. machines or clusters, runtime performance), temporary storage or bandwidth capabilities, etc. The execution of the test cases implies also defining which steps are executed manually, by the user, and to which level the process is automated. In addition, monitoring tools and principles are defined to acknowledge the status of the tests, for triggering early termination or for re-scheduling additional tests.

Last but not least, KPIs, as input to the virtual testing process, need to be measured and produced in the expected format and meaning. The simulation framework, components and resources shall be configured to guarantee the correct and timely acquisition of KPIs for the considered driving functions.

FIGURE 24: PART 1 OF THE PHASE "VIRTUAL TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Prepare virtual testing (see Figure 24):

The preparation of the virtual tests is the step where the necessary components, as identified in the strategy preparation, are set-up, configured or integrated into the simulation engine. This configuration must attend to the specified allocated test cases, so the virtual test indeed covers the set of tests described by the concrete scenario parameters and distributions.

Validate component (optional) (see Figure 25):

This step of the process is needed to validate the components that will take part in the execution of the virtual tests (ongoing work towards the standardisation of how such validation steps need to be given can be consulted at P.E.A.R.S [5]). Before any test is conducted, it is necessary to validate that the required components exist, are compatible with the simulation framework, that they do fit with the allocated test cases and that their simulated characteristics (e.g. physical, sensing or behavioural processes) represent with sufficient fidelity the characteristics of the simulated entities.

In general, the sequence of application of the different test methods should enable sharing test data results across methods (as defined in “Assign Testing Method Order” process step). Therefore, if the Proving Ground (PG) tests are carried out first, the results can feed the XiL test execution, at the validate component step, to consider any insights and outcome of the obtained PG test data necessary to fine-tune or reshape the preparation of XiL Tests. Analogously, XiL, along with PG tests data can be used during the virtual testing method execution.

This step of the process needs to be well aligned with the steps related to the creation of maps of capabilities of the different testing methods. In particular, the validation of components may imply the utilisation of interface languages or encapsulation mechanisms to connect models effectively from different vendors into the same simulation engine.

Conduct virtual tests (see Figure 25):

The execution of the tests is the step where the runtime engine of the simulation environment triggers the deployment of the scene, making use of the allocated processing power, the parameterized scene or set of scenes, dynamically connecting all software and hardware components to operate synchronously. The simulation is executed, monitored, visualised and eventually recorded to store the result log files in an appropriate format.

Test data is produced in this step, including logs about the scene execution, KPI-related metrics of the driving function(s) under test, and other metadata with links to the allocated test cases to guarantee the traceability of the results. Test data can be as detailed as necessary, depending on the test data management framework being used. For instance, runtime performance can also be stored and reported to identify processing bottlenecks; early termination situations triggered by exceptions or errors shall also be logged, allowing error handling processes.

Store test data (see Figure 25):

Test data is stored for the evaluation phase. The requirements for data storage shall consider aspects such as: traceability with executed test cases, the persistence of data, privacy and access rights, interpretability, and compatibility with data management platforms.

The utilisation of standards shall govern the selection of storage solutions, including standards for data formatting (e.g. OpenODS), meaning interpretation (e.g. OpenXOntology), but also good practices and technology trends in place (e.g. encryption and security, availability, archiving).

FIGURE 25: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "VIRTUAL TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Extract relevant parameters for evaluation (see Figure 26):

In this step, relevant information for the evaluation process is identified. Test data is post-processed to filter out parts of it which are not relevant (e.g. processing times, warnings or execution logs from internal simulation components, etc.), and may be redirected to an archiving solution. The relevant parameters for evaluation are those who directly or indirectly enable further comparison with KPIs as defined from the driving function under test.

Compare test data with KPI requirements (see Figure 26):

Once the tests have been carried out, and the relevant test data has been collected, relevant to the KPI of the driving function, the KPI can be evaluated.

This step needs to produce the comparison metrics according to the data format (units, ranges, quantities) of the KPIs. Relevant results are provided either for each single test case or for sets of test cases which share common characteristics or fall into an aggregate representative scene description.

FIGURE 26: PART 3 OF THE PHASE "VIRTUAL TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

7 XiL Testing

Mixed testing methods between real and virtually simulated environments are usually known as X-in-the-Loop (XiL). The combination of real and virtual elements covers cases such as HiL, Hardware-in-the-Loop, where a real driving ECU is integrated into a laboratory ecosystem of simulated elements, DiL, driver in the loop, where a real human driver is driving in a simulated environment; or VehiL, Vehicle-in-the-Loop, where an entire vehicle is immersed either into a virtual scene with some physical interface, and other participants are also simulated. To that end, sensor simulation is needed in most cases, so the simulated participants are injected at some point of the function-under-test, e.g. through an Open System Interface (OSI).

One of the main differences between XiL and virtual testing is that the real component (either the ECU, driver or the vehicle) implies the definition and utilisation of real-virtual interfaces with a real-time perspective. While purely virtual tests can be executed in batch at processor's clock speed, XiL needs to be sampled at the pace

mandated by the real component. As a consequence, this interface governs the number and volume of tests that can be executed with a given set of resources (time, computational, economic, and logistics). On the other hand, the ability to immerse a real component within a simulated environment gives one step closer to realism and fidelity, and as such, some components need no validation as being already real.

The overall process is analogous to the one described in the previous section virtual testing. Details are provided in the next table and sub-sections.

TABLE 7: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "XiL TESTING"

Phase: XiL Testing

Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner

Description: The strategy for the allocated scenarios, simulation models, and XiL infrastructure must be prepared. Then the tests can be conducted, and the test data will be processed to see if the results meet the KPI requirements.

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Allocated scenarios
- KPIs
- KPI requirements
- Proving ground test data (optional)

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Test data

Roles:

- XiL infrastructure owner
- Simulation model/environment owner
- Test engineer
- Data Manager

Resources or Assets:

- XiL infrastructure
- Simulation models
- Sensor models
- Simulation environment
- Proving ground test data (optional)
- Database

Phase: XiL Testing

Task:

- Prepare XiL testing strategy
- Prepare XiL testing
- Validate components (optional)
- Conduct XiL tests
- Store test data
- Extract relevant parameters for evaluation
- Compare test data with KPI requirements

Prepare XiL test plan (see Figure 27):

This step is similar to the preparation of a purely virtual testing strategy. XiL testing strategy preparation demands the (1) validation of components, the (2) identification of readiness of test cases, and (3) consideration of KPI for parameter selection and further comparison.

An essential perspective of the defined strategy is that real elements are used in the test, i.e. an ECU or vehicle under test. Therefore, logistic aspects need to be taken into consideration, to enable the utilisation of such components, allocate the human and economic resources needed, guarantee the status of the component previous to the test, etc.

In particular, the strategy shall address the schedule to run the tests in the appropriate time frame, as the utilisation of real components limit the ability to parallelize tests, obliged by the real-time nature of the component.

Also, the interface with the real component limits the amount of information that can be exchanged to and from the simulation environment. For instance, weather conditions, or V2X features might be virtually available at the simulator, but the real component cannot obtain such information directly, or the infrastructure utilised to install the real component does not have mechanisms to simulation certain features. Such limitations shall be appropriately addressed during the creation of the map of capabilities of the XiL test method.

Prepare XiL testing (see Figure 27):

Preparation of the XiL testing shall follow the same principles of the virtual testing, plus the required steps regarding the management of the real components, following the test strategy.

In this process step, the necessary components are set-up and are connected through appropriate interfaces. A test control layer is applied to orchestrate the interaction between the components during the test.

Similarly to the purely virtual testing method, manual steps are foreseen in this step.

FIGURE 27: PART 1 OF THE PHASE "XIL TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Validate component (optional, see Figure 28):

All simulated components shall follow the same validation principles as defined for the virtual testing modality. The addition is the utilisation of real components, such as a physical sensor, HMI, or the entire vehicle. In that sense, these components need not to be validated in the sense they are already real, and their fidelity with reality

is not under question. However, additional aspects may come into play, such as component maintenance, stability, operational conditions, etc.

FIGURE 28: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "XiL TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Conduct XiL tests (see Figure 28):

This step effectively executes the test under the defined conditions, using the validated components, and exercising the allocated test cases. Different XiL modalities imply different engineering set-ups. However, it involves the preparation of the real component, the interfaces and framework to interconnect it or immerse it into the simulation environment, and the virtual environment that runs the rest of the simulated elements.

As explained in previous sub-sections, the execution of the XiL shall follow the same principles defined for virtual testing.

Store test data (see Figure 28):

Storing test data for XiL shares the same principles defined for virtual testing test data storage. Some additional considerations may imply the utilisation of vendor-specific data and metadata containers, as produced by the real component (e.g. the specific ECU or vehicle under test). In such a case, data storing may also consider additional pre- or post-processing steps, for data unwrapping, conversion, encryption, etc.

Extract relevant parameters for evaluation (see Figure 29):

The extraction of relevant parameters should follow the sample principles as defined for virtual testing. However, specific parameters might be relevant when using real components such as an ECU or vehicle under test. For those allocated test cases, specific or more detailed KPIs might be produced.

Compare test data with KPI requirements (see Figure 29):

In general, the comparison of test data out of the XiL testing stage is equivalent to the one described for the purely virtual testing approach. However, depending on the driving function under analysis, there might be a significant difference regarding data labelling.

When data is simulated, e.g. from a virtual environment that renders a scene and is perceived (if a perception layer participates in the test), the ground truth of the perceived element is directly known and managed by the simulation environment, which always knows positions, velocities, and any other feature of all elements within the simulation. On the other hand, if a real component is used, some of the data might be real as well, e.g. images captured with a camera or with a laser scanner. Therefore, labelling the real data is necessary to have the ground truth figures that describe the elements of interest of the scene (e.g. presence, position, the volume of other participants, such as VRU or vehicles). The labelling process is known to be complex, costly, and that consumes much effort. If labelling is needed, then it needs to be aligned in terms of format, meaning, conventions and ranges with the metrics defined for the KPIs.

FIGURE 29: PART 3 OF THE PHASE "XIL TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

8 Proving Ground Testing

This part of the process is focused on the procedure for the execution of concrete test cases in proving grounds. Test cases have been previously allocated to this test environment by the allocation of scenarios and test case generation part of the process.

In track test testing, the vehicle-under-test is put in a realistic and controlled environment. Limitations result from the size of the track (speed limitation for vehicle-under-test and other road users), limited coverage of infrastructure layout, limited or no controllability of weather and lighting conditions. Advantage: realistic environment, very similar to real road testing. Some XiL testing is run on a proving ground

The number of scenarios to be executed in test tracks will be determined by the limitation of the simulation environments and the complexity of the automated driving use cases. This means that very complex driving events

should be reproduced in test tracks, and this increases the complexity of the proving grounds preparation for this purpose and the necessary equipment.

This new complex testing requirements for the proving grounds need to be managed in order to optimize the way how the allocated tests are executed in the best cost and time-effective manner.

TABLE 8: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "PROVING GROUND TESTING"

Phase: Proving Ground Testing

Phase Owner: Headstart Partner

Description: The strategy for the allocated scenarios, equipment and infrastructure must be prepared. Then the tests can be conducted, and the test data will be processed to see if the results meet the KPI requirements.

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Allocated scenarios
- KPIs
- KPI requirements

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Test data

Roles:

- Proving ground owner
- Test engineer
- Demonstrator car driver
- Data Manager

Resources or Assets:

- Proving ground
- Demonstrator car
- Targets
- Equipment (sensors, data logger, ...)
- Infrastructure (communications coverage, digital assets, ...)
- Database

Phase: Proving Ground Testing

Task:

- Prepare proving ground testing strategy
- Prepare equipment
- Prepare infrastructure
- Conduct proving ground tests
- Store test data
- Extract relevant parameters for evaluation
- Compare test data with KPI requirements

Prepare proving ground testing strategy (see Figure 30):

The first step of the process is to define the plan for the execution of the concrete scenarios in proving grounds. There are three primary inputs that need to be analysed before continuing with the procedure: the allocated concrete scenarios, the KPI's and KPI requirements

Once those requirements are defined for all the tests, the next step is set up a plan on how to execute the tests in the most cost and time-effective manner. For this purpose, the test cases which are basically a set of concrete scenarios organized in a sequential manner to be executed in the proving grounds need to be defined containing the acceptance criteria for each of them.

At the end of this activity, a test plan is defined, which should contain the following information:

- Vehicle Under Test equipment.
- Infrastructure equipment (dummies, communication infrastructure, digital maps, GNSS corrections ...)
- Test Cases (set of concrete scenarios with its acceptance criteria)

Prepare equipment (see Figure 30):

The goal of this activity is to prepare all the equipment which is necessary to install in the vehicle for the execution of the test cases in proving grounds.

For this purpose, it needs to be ensured that all the monitoring signals for the test cases of the vehicle under test are being recorded and also any equipment which is necessary for the synchronization between the vehicle under test and the infrastructure (for example with dummies) is taken into account.

During this activity, the equipment will be actually installed, and also commissioning of the vehicle under test will be done in order to ensure that everything works properly for conducting the tests.

FIGURE 30: PART 1 OF THE PHASE "PROVING GROUND TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Prepare infrastructure (see Figure 31):

During this activity, all equipment necessary for the execution of the test cases outside the vehicle will be prepared. This is one of the most critical activities in order to ensure the most cost and time-efficient strategy for the execution of the test cases. Those resources are not specific for the vehicle under test and need to be efficiently shared between test runs in order to improve the efficiency of the tests.

Conduct proving ground tests (see Figure 31):

Once the vehicle under test and the infrastructure are prepared, the tests are conducted on the test track. This activity will be generally conducted by a test engineer. For this reason, a test session document is generated for the test driver, which contains the definition of the test cases to be executed step by step in order to reduce the risk of misunderstandings.

FIGURE 31: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "PROVING GROUND TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Store test data (see Figure 31):

For this purpose, all the information relevant for the evaluation of the test cases is configured to be recorded.

Extract relevant parameters for evaluation (see Figure 32):

Each test case executed in the test track contains its acceptance criteria where the monitoring signals to be evaluated are defined. This information will be used to extract the information which is needed for the evaluation of each test case.

FIGURE 32: PART 3 OF THE PHASE "PROVING GROUND TESTING" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Compare test data with KPI requirements (see Figure 32):

The last step of the process is to evaluate the test cases executed in the test tracks. This activity will basically use the previously extracted data from the executed tests and compare them against the KPI requirements. For this purpose, a post-process needs to be done where it demonstrated if the test has passed or failed.

9 Cyber Security

According to HEADSTART project (Deliverable D2.1), the definition of cyber security is “the protection of connected systems including hardware, software and data from internal and external attacks carried by malicious entities with or without authorization”. The HEADSTART process includes the cyber security assessment. In this project, cyber security is considered a KET, along with positioning and communication. Because of the characteristics of cyber security assessment, HEADSTART provides a separate process to assess cyber security in parallel to the other parts of the assessment.

This chapter presents a brief overview of cyber security as a KET and explains why it has a special treatment compared to the other two KETs. Then, a summary of cyber security in the methodology is included to have a better understanding of the process. After an introduction, the chapter describes in detail the cyber security assessment as part of the entire process. The process introduces a unique cyber security assessment branch that covers the full cyber security assessment and integrates different roles for use cases and target groups. In the end, the cyber security tool that will be used for the next steps is presented.

TABLE 9: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "CYBER SECURITY"

Phase: Cyber Security

Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner

Description: All cyber security related tests that cannot be allocated to scenarios are prepared, conducted and evaluated here

Entry Criteria/Inputs:

- Set of criteria
- Threat analysis and risk assessment
- Cyber security related test data from testing methods

Exit Criteria/Outputs:

- Test data

Roles:

- Driving function owner
- Driving function cyber security developer
- Test engineer

Resources or Assets:

- Cyber security asset
- Test data

Task:

- Select generic security needs (protection profile)
- Define the target of evaluation
- Generate specific security needs for the target of evaluation (security target)
- Select cyber security requirements for testing
- Integrate testing result into security target
- Evaluate security target (testing lab)
- Assign evaluation assurance levels (testing lab)

9.1 Cyber security as a KET

Connected and Automated Driving functions may be vulnerable to a wide range of attacks. They may affect the communication towards connected and/or cooperating vehicles, the intra-vehicle communication among integrated third-party parts, generally any X2V/V2V/V2X communication or they may affect the proper positioning of the ego vehicle. This situation endangers the safety of automated vehicles and turns cyber security as a pre-requisite to validate and assess CAD functions.

Consequently, under HEADSTART's scope, cyber security is considered as a key enabling technology (KET) along with positioning and communication. Safety of the vehicle cannot be guaranteed without cyber security; thus it needs a special treatment to be integrated into the safety assessment. In contrast to the other two KETs, it is difficult to measure and apply any type of performance indicators or extract relevant parameters for testing purposes, since in practice cyber security is directly applied to communication and positioning in several ways.

The reasoning for treating cyber security as a KET is that it is equally essential to the others, given that HEADSTART intends to propose a validation and assessment procedure. In other words, such a procedure cannot be safe and valid if cyber security requirements are not met. Even if functionally an automated vehicle can operate without cyber security (level-0 security), it will only remain a theoretical proof of concept which cannot become accepted under HEADSTART's assessment procedure.

When treating cyber security as a KET, it should be considered throughout the lifecycle of the process as such. Starting from the identification of the threats and vulnerabilities to the application of countermeasures and safety tests, one has to establish structured development processes, and finally define suitable assessment procedures to test, validate and certify CAD safety. For this purpose, existing best practices and tools are considered and exploited from relevant initiatives.

9.2 Cyber security in the methodology

The proposed HEADSTART methodology is explained in D2.1, while the inclusion of KETs is detailed in D2.2. Within this methodology, the concrete scenarios are enhanced with KET parameters, one of which is cyber security, as indicated in Figure 33.

FIGURE 33: METHODOLOGY AND CYBER SECURITY KET PARAMETERS

The identified cyber security parameters are shown in Figure 34. As indicated there, cyber security is mostly bound to the other two KETs, positioning and communication. Figure 35 shows in detail the flow of cyber security within the methodology.

The concrete scenarios that are qualified for further assessment by HEADSTART methodology are injected with specific cyber security parameters. For example, in an identified concrete scenario, a V2X jammer may be applied. That is a generator able to generate fake vehicles around the vehicle under test. Depending on the results, the scenario may be either re-iterated in the HEADSTART methodology with altered parameters or move to the next steps as a stochastically varied scenario, towards its allocation to a test instance (e.g. proving ground). Intermediate steps to explore cyber security requirements and to generate a test case may include conformance tests to well-known safety and security standards, interoperability tests, vulnerability scanning, functional and penetration tests. The inclusion of such parameters turns the initial scenario to a concrete KET enhanced scenario ready for testing, ultimately leading to the evaluation part of the methodology.

This KET will be presented as a relatively independent branch within the proposed process in the next section.

FIGURE 34: SCENARIO KETS PARAMETERS

FIGURE 35: CYBER SECURITY FLOW WITHIN HEADSTART METHODOLOGY

9.3 Cyber security in the process

The process integrates the cyber security KET into the safety assessment in a separate branch. To adequately cover cyber security, this separate branch addresses three different levels of cyber security coverage:

1. The first level addresses cyber security by enriching the (relevant) concrete scenarios adding scenario parameters that, after the testing allocation, will be transformed into different testing methods like penetration test, fuzzy test, vulnerability scanning, functionality testing, etc. Therefore, this level provides a way of testing cyber security requirements.
2. The second level extends the first level to include intended functionalities related to cyber security (e.g. malicious interferences of a sensor, etc.). The steps are the same, but the enrichment of the concrete scenario is based on specific intended functionality parameters (see Figure 36).
3. The third level addresses cyber security as a product lifecycle management. The product lifecycle management put together all specific activities for cyber security risk management regarding engineering for concept phase, product development and post-development phase, risk assessment and continuous cyber security activities. The purpose of this level is to cover all the activities required for product lifecycle at the vehicle level for cyber security validation.

FIGURE 36: SOTIF AND CYBER SECURITY

Cyber security is represented in the process as an independent branch (see Figure 37) and defines the required steps to assess cyber security. The cyber security branch is part of the process, but it is not mandatory to execute it. It could be considered as an “extension” of the process, although its use is highly recommended.

FIGURE 37: CYBER SECURITY IN THE PROCESS

The cyber security branch is designed to integrate all levels of cyber security coverage. To achieve this, the cyber security process bases its activities on the Common Criteria activities. The Common Criteria (CC) is an international standard for evaluating the security properties of IT products. The CC defines a framework for evaluation oversight, the structure for specifying security requirements that must be fulfilled, and a methodology for evaluating those requirements. In this framework, users can specify their Security Functional Requirements (SFRs) and Security functional Assurance Requirements (SARs) using Protection Profiles (PPs). Target groups can implement and request security attributes of their products, e.g. into vehicle-specific cyber security assets, and hire testing laboratories to evaluate their products and determine if they meet these requirements.

The CC provides assurance that the product lifecycle management (specification, implementation and evaluation) has been conducted in a rigorous, standard and repeatable manner. Furthermore, the CC is used by governments

and other organizations around the world to assess the security of information technology products, and it is the basis for a government-driven certification scheme. Evaluations are typically completed by the government agencies, and once this process is completed successfully, a vendor achieves Common Criteria certification.

The cyber security branch is represented in Figure 38 and is triggered when the process evaluates the driving functionality (Dynamic Driving Task) connected to cyber security assets. This means that every time cyber security is required in the safety validation process for CAD vehicles, the cyber security branch must be executed.

Select generic security needs (protection profile) / Define target of evaluation (see Figure 38):

The cyber security process requires as an input the necessary information to describe the item, the system that will be evaluated. This information should be provided by the developer of the item involved in the driving function development in order to assess cyber security with all the required information. After that, two main activities are executed: the selection of the generic security needs and the description of the system for which cyber security is evaluated: Target of Evaluation (TOE).

The first activity is the selection of what is called in CC the Protection Profiles. The PP identifies generic security requirements for a group of security devices (for example, Firewall Protection Profiles used to provide security requirements for network devices) relevant to the user for a particular purpose. It is typically created by a user or user community and provides an independent implementation of information assurance security requirements. A PP is a combination of threats, security objectives, assumptions, SFRs, SARs and rationales. Those responsible for carrying out this activity should assess whether there exists a PP for their system and, if so, they may choose to implement one or more PPs. A PP specifies generic security evaluation criteria and, among others, it typically specifies the Evaluation Assurance Level (EAL), indicating the depth and rigor of the security evaluation.

The second activity is the definition of the Target of Evaluation (TOE). The TOE defines the item or system of evaluation for our process; however, CC extend that definition as a set of software, firmware and/or hardware possibly accompanied by guidance. As example a TOE can be a software application, an operating system, a smart card integrated circuit, the cryptographic co-processor of a smart card integrated circuit, a local area network including all terminals, servers, network equipment and software, a database application, etc. Here the TOE is the systems connected to the CAD function and cyber security of the vehicle-under-test.

Generate specific security needs for the target of evaluation (security target) (see Figure 38):

The next step is the generation of specific security needs for the target of evaluation, what is called in CC the Security Target (ST). For that task it is necessary to include all the information prepared from the first activities, the selected PP, the definition of the TOE and all the relevant information such Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) focus on the vehicle level and the defined KPIs. TARA provides a list of generic threats to consider when defining the ST while KPIs define the risk tolerance and will influence the final EALs determination.

The ST is the implementation-dependent statement of security needs and defines information assurance security and functional requirements for a specific identified TOE. An ST is a complete and rigorous description of a security problem in terms of TOE description, threats, assumptions, security objectives, SFRs, SARs, and rationales. An ST contains information that demonstrates how the product addresses the security requirements based on the generic security requirements given in each of these PPs. The ST includes a target group self-assessment detailing how the product conforms to the relevant PP at the EAL the target group chooses to test against.

FIGURE 38: CYBER SECURITY INDEPENDENT BRANCH

Select cyber security requirements for testing / Integrate testing results into security target (see Figure 38):

The ST activity provides proof that the product complies with SFRs, which is supported by documentation and testing. To support the testing part for SFRs, the next step determines which requirements are available for allocation on the general validation test process. This step connects cyber security testing activities with the different testing methods available to validate CAD vehicles and thus be able to test cyber security in multiple scenarios. The results of the tests will be collected at the end of the process and integrated into the ST. The ST integration results represent the final document that will be provided to the independent laboratories.

Evaluate security target (testing lab) / Assign evaluation assurance levels (testing lab) (see Figure 38):

Product certificates are awarded by national schemes based on validation carried by independent testing laboratories. Therefore, CC establishes the role of independent laboratories to certify the defined TOE. A CC testing laboratory is a third-party commercial security testing facility that is accredited to conduct security evaluations for conformance to the CC international standard. Such a facility must be accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025 with its national certification body and comply with the specific requirements enforced by each country.

The final steps of the cyber security branch are connected to the independent testing lab activities. The CC evaluation authority conducts two main tasks, the evaluation of the Security Target and the assignment of the Evaluation Assurance Levels. The purpose is to convince that the item complies with all the defined SARs and its claimed functionalities for the particular EAL, and with the required SFRs.

The evaluation process tries to establish the level of confidence that may be placed in the item's security features through quality assurance processes. The evaluation of the ST performs all necessary work to evaluate the ST according to its SFRs. This step takes the SARs taken during development for the defined assure level as a reference, to be able to validate the FSRs and their identified dependencies. The assignment of the EALs evaluates if the EALs are achieved for the defined assure level established for the TOE. The EAL defines the depth and rigour of the security evaluation of SARs and is typically given as a number 1 through 7. The CC lists seven levels, with EAL 1 being the most basic (and therefore cheapest to implement and evaluate) and EAL 7 being the most stringent (and most expensive).

Finally, the results of the independent testing laboratories, together with the ST report are grouped together for a final report result. The final report is the end of the process and will be the output of the process (see more information in the evaluation section). However, CC has the role of evaluation and validation scheme. The scheme is a government agency that sets the security rules for validation an evaluation of the analysed item or product. For example, in the United States, it is the National Security Agency, in Germany the "Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik", and so on. These Schemes configure what is called, the Validation Body, which has the ultimate responsibility for the product certification. The Validation Body ensures that appropriate mechanisms are in place to protect the interests of all parties participating in the process of the TOE evaluation.

This cyber security process is based on the CC methodology basically because it is the only standard entirely focused on certification products (ISO/IEC 15408). However, the automotive industry addresses the cyber security in engineering of electrical and electronic (E/E) systems within road vehicles in ISO/SAE 21434. The standard provides vocabulary, objectives, requirements and guidelines as a foundation for common understanding throughout the supply chain. Both standards are different. Nevertheless, they share common activities to assess cyber security and both propose best practices for protecting items, systems, products against unauthorized access or attack.

9.4 Target groups role in the process

The CC introduce different roles and responsibilities during the evaluation process that should be clarified according to the target groups of the HEADSTART project. There are three major roles in the CC process, the Developers, the Laboratory and the Certification Body. The Developers are responsible for the first part of the process, from the generic selection of the security need (PP) and the definition of the TOE to the final results of the ST. This role represents OEMs and Tier-n suppliers in HEADSTART. Laboratories are responsible of the evaluation of the ST and assignment of the EAL and, as in the CC standard, are represented by independent laboratories or research organizations in HEADSTART. Finally, the third role is represented by the Certification Body, which provides the certification of the cyber security evaluation. In our project, this role is represented by the type-approval authorities.

9.5 Cyber security test tool

One specific scope of the project is to explore existing tools that can be adopted and used in the proposed HEADSTART's methodology. A concrete option for cyber security stems from SaferTEC, an H2020 project which

relies on Common Criteria adopted to the automotive sector and which has proposed a Security Assessment Framework.

Provisionally identified to belong to TRL 3 category, HEADSTART will try to forward this Framework to at least one level further. Being coordinated by HEADSTART's partner ICCS, that project's insights will be analysed to lead to a synergy according to current methodology needs.

Acknowledging though that the task of creating a completely customized tool to meet the requirements of the project is quite difficult within the restricted resources of the project, the tangible goal would be to spend effort in trying to adjust the existing Framework through developing and customization, producing this way a generic tool that could support a few indicative cases of HEADSTART's methodology. However, the result of the readiness of the tool may ultimately differ to that of a complete tool, and still need to apply several assumptions to be used in the proposed methodology.

10 Evaluation

The general procedure ends with the "Evaluation" phase. The evaluation phase starts with a definition of key performance indicators (KPIs) that are used to generate target group requirements together with information about dynamic driving task (DDT), the operational design domain (ODD), the use case and the threat analysis and risk assessment. The next step is to define how the key performance indicators are verified before the testing is conducted. After which the actual evaluations start, where result parameters are matched with KPI requirements and a verdict for the tests is produced. All information is then aggregated and presented in a report.

The necessary input for this phase is a relevant KPI and criteria for verification thereof, together with relevant test results.

TABLE 10: PHASE DESCRIPTION FOR "EVALUATION"

Phase: Evaluation
Phase Owner: HEADSTART Partner
Description: Test data are compared to the KPI requirements to assess the results
Entry Criteria/Inputs:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic driving tasks • Use case • Target group requirements • Test data
Exit Criteria/Outputs:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set of KPIs • Set of criteria • Report of the evaluated test data

Phase: Evaluation

Roles:

- Driving function owner
- Target group
- Test engineer
- Data manager
- Report author

Resources or Assets:

- Test data

Tasks:

- Define KPIs
 - Define KPI verification
 - Extract relevant parameters for evaluation (overlapping with other phases)
 - Compare test data with KPI requirements (overlapping with other phases)
 - Combine test results for decision making
 - Report results
-

Define KPIs (see Figure 39):

The key performance indicators (KPIs) are generated using target group requirements together with information about dynamic driving task (DDT), the operational design domain (ODD) and the use case. The KPI should be selected to have a specific purpose for the target group. In order to be able to generate a set of criteria, the KPIs must be adapted to be measurable and being quantitative and with achievable norms. In addition, the KPIs must be defined such that they are observable to a high degree of confidence in the test results.

Define KPI verification (see Figure 39):

The defined KPIs will be used to verify the selected criteria for each target group. The verification should be done to produce test results from all scenarios defined for the functions, and with data for each applicable KPI for each scenario and should result in a summary of passed or failed evaluation criteria or a sliding scale if applicable. Each KPI should have a set of expected relevant test results.

FIGURE 39 : PART 1 OF THE PHASE "EVALUATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

Extract relevant parameters for evaluation (overlapping with other phases) (see Figure 40):

For each testing method, a large amount of test data will be produced. A relevance analysis has been performed before each test method has been conducted to address storage issues. For some test purposes, there is a need for combining parameters from different testing methods, that first after a merge is fulfilling the aspect of being relevant for further analysis. Such testing methods parameter overlap needs to be considered in a preceding part of the procedure.

Compare test data with KPI requirements (overlapping with other phases) (see Figure 40):

The final step for each test is to compare the extracted test data with defined KPI requirements. Thereby the subset of the test data is chosen that is relevant to be used as input for combining all test data in the following step.

FIGURE 40: PART 2 OF THE PHASE "EVALUATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS (OVERLAPPING WITH PARTS OF THE TESTING PHASES)

Combine test results for decision making (see Figure 41):

A compilation of test results is needed to determine if the KPIs have been met for the function and thus provide a basis for a decision regarding its suitability for the intended purpose. The raw data for this compilation is the comparison of test results with KPI verification criteria from the previous step. It is vital that the compilation can show the coverage of tests. Hence it should be verified that the compilation contains results from all scenarios initially defined for the function, and that data for each applicable KPI has been obtained for each scenario.

The compilation includes results from the four safety testing methods and the security testing lab.

A summary with statistics on coverage and passed or failed evaluation criteria should be included, and any failed criteria should be highlighted. Depending on how the KPIs and their criteria for evaluation were defined, it might also be necessary to combine evaluation criteria into other forms of results than a simple pass or fail, e.g. statistical data. The summary will be part of the final test report.

Report results (see Figure 41):

A comprehensive way to report the test results is important, especially since the tests are assumed to generate large amounts of recorded data. Test data from field tests, virtual tests, XiL tests and proving ground tests will be combined with the results of the security evaluation. A comprehensive report should be compiled. The results shall be provided accurately, clearly, unambiguously and objectively. Review and authorisation of the results shall be performed prior to the release of the report.

The report shall include a description of the testing methods and the test object. A reference for the test method can be made to international standards or publicly available documents. In case the testing method is not publicly available, the report will have to describe the performance. The test object must be described, and unambiguously identified, especially if it is a prototype with subsystems under development.

The results are, of course, an essential part of the report. In most cases, the test data will not be included in the report. The results presented in the report will be a summary of the recorded test data. When measurements are included, the unit of measurement and the measurement uncertainty shall be stated. When a statement of conformity to a specification or standard is provided, the report shall explain how the decision was made. A

statement on fulfilment of a KPI must also be accompanied by an explanation of why the KPI can be judged as fulfilled.

The test laboratory performing the test must be stated, and the person(s) authorizing the report clearly identified. The date(s) of performance of the test activity and the date of issue of the report must also be included.

FIGURE 41 PART 3 OF THE PHASE "EVALUATION" OF THE DETAILED PROCESS

11 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the further development of the HEADSTART methodology that was worked out in work package 2. The methodology has been transformed in several steps into a process, which has been represented in detail on the basis of a UML activity diagram. This process was then formulated as a procedure in the chapters of this report. The chapters represent the individual phases of the procedure, and each of the process steps contained therein was described. This serves as a guide to enable the process to be actually carried out. The methodology is still not finished to this date since new aspects appear along the way that request changes. This applies to the HEADSTART procedure as well. An attempt was made to create an accurate process that includes and takes into account as many aspects as possible. Nevertheless, some things could not be described in a necessary detail at this time. Some things, like data formats and interfaces, will be defined in more detail later in the project. Perhaps, in the course of the project and during the validation of the procedure, gaps will be discovered that were overlooked in theory. These have to be corrected later on.

The Key Enabling Technologies (V2X communication, positioning and cyber security). Since it was not possible to use the same process steps for all three KETs, they had to be dealt with differently. Communication and positioning could be integrated into the main process most of the time. Only in the Scenario Allocation phase did these technologies have to be treated separately. This was solved with a separate branch in the process, which, however, is very strongly linked to the main process. Cyber Security, on the other hand, has different requirements and was therefore dealt with in a separate phase.

An important aspect in the development of the process was to integrate the KETs into the process steps in a most natural way. This has been achieved in many parts of the process. Communication and positioning requirements can almost always be processed in the general tasks. Only in the Scenario Allocation phase was it necessary to create a separate branch in order to ensure correct execution. Cyber Security, on the other hand, requires a significantly different structure. Therefore a separate branch was developed, which is nevertheless connected to the main part of the process.

The breakdown into the nine phases is an essential point in the procedure. This results in a structure that is intended to help in the execution of the process. Scenario Selection and Scenario Allocation are two essential phases. They are the starting point for the successful execution of the procedure. However, there are still some uncertainties. This already starts with the fact that there is no standard for the formulation of the ODD yet. This makes it difficult to predict how to check if the selected scenarios are inside the ODD or if the ODD is already sufficiently covered. Without standards, it is not possible to automate this procedure, and many of the tasks have to be performed manually by experts. Even scenario databases do not yet have a standardised way of retrieving information. The question of the data formats that are returned and how to link different data formats will be a focus in the further course of this work package. The availability of parameter distributions is also still unclear. Can this information be obtained from the scenarios database? How do you handle it if they have to be added manually? In cases like these, the procedure depends on the practical application.

The role of the target groups also has to be evaluated in practice. In many places in the process, important decisions are made by these groups. In theory, this is important and makes sense. How this will be handled in practice, and whether different target groups may want to intervene to different degrees in the process, is not known at present.

There are still questions regarding evaluation. How exactly should the test results be presented, and should the final evaluation be part of the procedure? The process shows a way how this could be done.

The procedure, like the methodology, is something that can and will change and refine in the course of the project. This deliverable presents the current procedure and describes it in the highest possible level of detail on which further work in the project can be based.

References

- [1] 3. SAE J, "Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to On-Road Motor Vehicle Automated Driving Systems," 2018.
- [2] ISO 26262, "Road Vehicles - Functional Safety," 2018.
- [3] HEADSTART D2.1 Overall methodology.
- [4] Laporte, Claude & Chevalier, Frédéric. (2016). *An Innovative Approach to the Development of Project Management Processes for Small-Scale Projects in a Large Engineering Company*. 10.4018/978-1-4666-9737-9..
- [5] PEGASUS, "PEGASUS Method - An Overview," 2019.
- [6] B. Schwab, C. Beil and T. Kolbe, "Spatio-Semantic Road Space Modeling for Vehicle–Pedestrian Simulation to Test Automated Driving Systems," *Sustainability - Volume 12*, p. 3799, May 2020.
- [7] Peter Wimmer, Michael Düring, Henri Chajmowicz, Fredrik Granum, Julian King, Harald Kolk, Olaf Op den Camp, Paolo Scognamiglio & Michael Wagner (2019) *Toward harmonizing prospective effectiveness assessment for road safety: Comparing tools in standard tes*.

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